

UDC 338.012

AGRIS: E 14

JEL classification: A 13, E 22, F 02, H 87

WAYS OF BALANCED AGRICULTURAL MARKET DEVELOPMENT

ПУТИ СБАЛАНСИРОВАННОГО РАЗВИТИЯ АГРАРНОГО РЫНКА

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Abstract. This article introduces scientific and theoretical ideas that increase agricultural production efficiency can be achieved by ensuring a balanced supply of agricultural products, agribusinesses and agro services that are part of the agricultural market. The author has studied the issues of balanced development of agricultural products, agribusinesses and agro services in the agrarian sphere within the framework of the free market law.

Аннотация. В этой статье представлены научные и теоретические идеи, которые могут повысить эффективность сельскохозяйственного производства путем обеспечения сбалансированного предложения сельскохозяйственной продукции, агробизнеса и агросетей, которые являются частью сельскохозяйственного рынка. Автор изучил вопросы сбалансированного развития сельскохозяйственной продукции, агробизнеса и агросетей в аграрной сфере в рамках закона о свободном рынке.

Keywords: agricultural trade policy, agricultural products market, agricultural resource market, agricultural services market, free economic competition, innovative ideas, innovative agricultural technologies.

Ключевые слова: сельскохозяйственная торговая политика, рынок сельскохозяйственной продукции, рынок агроресурсов, рынок агросетей, свободная экономическая конкуренция, инновационные идеи, инновационные агротехнологии.

Introduction

The demand and demand for agricultural products in our country today can not guarantee the commodity producer's ability to sell its products at high prices and to benefit from high profits. Because of this it is necessary to have access to well-stocked warehouses, a well-maintained transport system, a competitive environment, as well as commercial vehicles and procurement plants, and to develop agricultural processing industries with new technologies. In particular, the lack of competitive environment in the system of procurement and processing enterprises has a negative impact on the economic situation of fruit and vegetable, dairy farming and dekhkan farms.

The expected outcome can not be achieved without ensuring the balanced development of agricultural markets, agribusinesses and agro services, which are part of the agrarian market. For

example, it is directly linked to the development of agribusiness and agro services markets for agricultural production and high returns. At present, the agrarian sector's lack of access to major types of resources in the agrarian sector and the priority of resource-driven industries prevent the distribution of resources on free market principles.

Opportunities to increase the economic efficiency of resource utilization in the conditions of free economic competition arise as a result of independent activities for the benefit of agricultural producers, resource makers and service providers.

Usually, businesses in the agrarian sector will continue to utilize their resources until the maximal margin of costs associated with products and services is equivalent to the average market value of products and services. This is the classical requirement of the market, which forms the basis of independent economic activity of the market subject.

Literature review

Agrarian economics academics, including K. Enderson [2], L. Gilbert, Y. Ramkishen [3], F. Kotler, K. McConnell [4] and others, in the field of agricultural production, agrosurria and agro services, S. Bryu, N. Kovalenko [5], A. Orlov [6], V. Yakovets [7], I. Dobrynin, I. Makarets [8], F. Shakirova and others. In the Republic of Uzbekistan, the agricultural sector has been actively involved in the use of the system's potential, including: R. Husanov, F. Qayumov, Q. Choriev [10], A. Jo'raev [11], N. Hushmatov [12], U. Omurzokov, K. Ubaydullaev, N. Hushmatov, R. Abdullayev [13], A. Kodirov [14], Ch. Murodov [15], E. Yusupov [16], U. Nigmatjanov [17], I. Rajabov [18], T. Farmonov, F. Nazarova [19], Q. Tursinov, T. Ch. Shodiev, I. Rafikov. However, the above-mentioned authors' scientific works were carried out in the early years of the independence of the country and within the framework of the priorities of the country's next stage of reform of the economy, and nowadays do not fully cover the innovative model of development and modernization of the country's economy. Also, taking into consideration the negative impact of global financial and natural climatic changes on the planet today, the lack of full coverage of these issues, and the scientifically-practical research on justifying scientific solutions of the technological modernization of the country's agrarian sector. to go. The aforementioned authors focus on researching economic issues in the agrarian sector, from a particular market (from production to production to consumer), which does not cover the complex development and maintenance of proportionality. Specifically, the analysis of the types of services currently provided in agriculture, as well as the volume and value of the work done, indicate that the non-compliance of the service sector with agricultural commodity producers is hampering the development of agriculture, while the economic condition of agricultural enterprises determines the development of services. Therefore, due to the development of agricultural product markets, the agro services markets, and the agribusiness market, the development of business entities, the competitiveness of service structures, improving the scientific and theoretical foundations of the internal economic relations of the service companies are becoming topical. Taking into account the above, the necessity to study the issues related to the harmonious development of agrarian, agricultural and agro-services markets in the framework of the free market law, and the necessity of making scientific and methodological recommendations for the balanced development of these markets was the basis for this topic.

Analyze and discussion

Agricultural enterprises provide a simple and extensive reproduction and profit-making opportunity for industrial enterprises and service providers. At the same time, there is a distribution of resources, which will allow satisfying the needs of consumers of agricultural products, resources,

and services at the same time. Attracting investment in agrarian sector production and services will be attractive.

The peculiarity of the economy and the competition in the market are primarily aimed at saving resources on production of goods and services and preventing excess costs. It is the simplest and most effective way of gaining precedence over the competitive struggle and continuing the production process. Because the increasing labor productivity and product quality require complex technology, equipping production with cutting-edge technologies is a fast-paced task for developing countries, requiring a large number of financial resources and time.

In order to gain dominance in the free market competition, the agrarian market entities should have not only modern technologies, but also professionals with the ability to work in a competitive, free market environment. Such a situation is one of the factors leading to rapid growth of the national economy and improvement of production relations.

Economic efficiency of farming and dehkan farms is characterized by pure economic and financial results, which are generally derived from the use of resource consumption resources in agriculture. As the main source of agriculture, land and labor inputs, economic, statistical and legal discrepancies in the use of labor resources in farming and dehkan farms, reduces the reliability of labor resources as an object of economic analysis (the actual use of labor resources and the system of labor accounting imperfection). Therefore, it is expedient to use agricultural land as a key resource for analyzing the economic efficiency of resources.

Provision of balanced development of agricultural products, agribusinesses and agro services markets is reflected in the effectiveness of production within the farmers and dehkan farms, particularly in the form of agrotechnological arrangements, resource utilization, and efficiency of socio-economic processes.

The efficiency of production within the agricultural enterprises reflects the qualitative and quantitative results of resource utilization, including production (agricultural crop yields, livestock productivity, labor productivity, etc.), agrotechnological (timely and qualitative agro technical arrangements on crop cultivation economic indicators (benefits, profitability, profitability due to resource utilization), social indicators (average The amount of a salary, economic and social conditions for employees, etc.) will be evaluated.

Within the farming and dehkan farms, production efficiency is primarily manifested through a resource-saving system. This is due to the fact that the competitiveness of the agribusiness market is dependent on the quality of resources and the average market value of the agricultural sector. That is, the farmer can only create economical and economical production within the framework of the production process, equipped with modern technology and technology. This requires the use of modern technology and technology at a relatively low prices and an agrarian market that guarantees delivery to farmers through an effective system. In other words, the level of resource provision of agricultural production determines the efficiency of production and vice versa. Therefore, in evaluating the effectiveness of agricultural production, the level of development of the services and supply of resources is also required.

Hence, the increase in production and quality of agricultural production should largely be achieved through the effective allocation and use of resources through the market system. Because farmers and dehkan farms have limited financial resources, there is a reduction in purchasing power and solvency, which in turn results in lower productivity.

Increasing the economic efficiency of agricultural production in farms and dehkan farms is determined not only by high-tech modern machinery, machinery, technology, production mechanization, the broader use of scientific and technological progress, but also by the social

conditions of production. It is important to improve the skills and abilities of specialists in agriculture and to improve their spiritual level, to improve the mechanism of financial incentives, and, in other words, activate the human factor.

While the impact of farmers and dehqan farmers activities on agricultural productivity, agro-market and agro-services markets has been evident, there are a number of factors that make the impact of their impact assessed by market demand and supply rules more sophisticated. In particular, economic relations with farmers and dehqan farms can be influenced by direct market mechanisms (see Figure 1), resulting from the use of services, including the use of resources for production, the use of continuous and seasonal workforce, services for agricultural production and services.

However, in addition to the factors that affect the productivity of production, the ability to manage production and the entrepreneurial skill of decision-makers (private owners) are crucial to establishing agricultural production. Also, the geographical location of the farming lands and the rent factors within the sown areas are also affected.

The impact of factors selected as the main and most effective impacts on the level of development of existing productive forces in the country has been quantitatively expressed by the expert evaluation of impacts on the final agricultural outcomes. Particularly, the level of supply of material and technical resources as the main factor influencing the output of the farms (27% of the author's expert estimates) is highlighted.

In the conditions that the development of the agribusiness market does not meet the requirements of the manufacturer, the manufacturer will benefit from this industry's activity. In this regard, other factors were also evaluated with numbers. However, these expert assessments are subjectivity assessments based on the author's observations, analyzes, and change in the necessary conditions for agricultural production, as well as changing trends in the development of different markets.

The location of agricultural production within the venue, regional varieties, and supply breakdowns with agrosources limit the rapid and sharp increase in economic efficiency of production. In this connection, it is possible to increase the cost-effectiveness of production using regional resource potential (provinces of natural, climatic, irrigation, labor, energy, etc.) on the basis of free market requirements.

The interconnection of agricultural products, agribusiness and agro services markets shows that the low demand for resources in the domestic market results not only in resource prices, but also in the decline in the aggregate capacity of agricultural enterprises, as well as the decline in production volumes. At the same time, it should be noted that the link between agrosources and agricultural markets is directly related to the relationship between most agro services markets and agricultural product markets. Therefore, one of the most important issues in raising productivity in farming and dehqan farms is resource provision. Particularly, the rational use of land resources, which is an important part of resources, depends primarily on the implementation of agricultural plots by region, taking into account the existing conditions and market demand.

Increasing the cost-effectiveness of agricultural production requires not only the introduction of additional land plots, but also primarily due to fertility, crop yields, and labor incentives. At the same time, the issue of improving the efficiency of agricultural production requires the provision of adequate and economically viable agriculture and modern equipment.

Free market principles are important because of the inefficient economic mechanisms in the agrarian and market-oriented markets, the elimination of their activities, and the economically profitable sectors that contribute to the sustainable development of their material and labor costs.

However, it should be noted that the profit or loss received by enterprises does not lead to the distribution of resources in the form and proportion that always meets the general consumer demand in the society as a set of economic relations.

Source: It has been produced under the author resources.

Figure. Mechanisms and Effects of Effect on Agricultural Productivity Level on Developing Agroresurs, Agro-Services Markets

It was emphasized that the state's coordinating tasks are used. However, the presence of elements of entrepreneurship activity in the markets of agricultural products, agribusinesses and agro services, the intensification of production and services specialization, the maximization of the consumer needs of the market, the increase in the profitability by saving production costs incentives.

Conclusion

Ensuring balance between the development of agricultural products, agribusinesses and agro services markets has an impact on the effectiveness of production within the farming and dehkan farms, first of all, in our opinion:

- reflecting the relations formed within the framework of different aspects and the economic nature of increasing the productivity through the system of economic indicators;

- From the point of view of the link between dialectic development, it must be objectively reflecting all the elements of the system of production relations in the interconnected, the quality and quantity of production results, and other indicators of resource utilization;

- the dependence of agricultural production on the level of development of the market of services and services, and on the contrary, the development of services and agro-market markets depends on the level of agricultural development;

- the development of agricultural products, agribusinesses and agro-services markets, should reflect the factors, causes, capacities and efficiency of the existing economic risks in farming and dehkan farms.

To sum up, there is a need to ensure a balanced distribution of agricultural products, agribusinesses and agro services, increase in the volume of agricultural products at agricultural enterprises, and their high returns.

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*Работа поступила
в редакцию 11.04.2018 г.*

*Принята к публикации
16.04.2018 г.*

Cite as (APA):

Aliev, Ya. (2018). Ways of balanced agricultural market development. *Bulletin of Science and Practice*, 4(5), 406-413.

Ссылка для цитирования:

Aliev Ya. Ways of balanced agricultural market development // Бюллетень науки и практики. 2018. Т. 4. №5. С. 406-413. Режим доступа: <http://www.bulletennauki.com/aliev-ya> (дата обращения 15.05.2018).